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What determines the Arctic solar radiation energy budget at the surface most strongly: Clouds, surface albedo, or the solar zenith angle?

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ABSTRACT

Cloud total water path (TWP), surface albedo (α), and solar zenith angle (SZA) are the main parameters driving the solar radiative energy budget (REB) at the surface in the Arctic. We have used results of simulations with a coupled Arctic regional climate model to quantify the spatio-temporal sensitivity of the solar REB at the surface with respect to changes of these three parameters. The simulations covered the period of polar day during the Multidisciplinary drifting Observatory for the Study of Arctic Climate (MOSAIC) expedition in 2020. Two methods have been employed to quantify the relative impact of the variability of the three parameters: a standardized regression method and a machine learning algorithm. Both approaches provided similar sensitivities of the solar REB at the surface with respect to cloud TWP, α , and SZA. Averaged over the period from April to September 2020, the SZA appeared as the most important factor determining changes of the solar REB at the surface. However, its relative influence exhibited the lowest spatial variability over the Arctic area as compared to the relative impact of cloud TWP and α . In spring, after the onset of melting, when the cloud TWP was still relatively low, the relative effect of surface albedo variability dominated the changes of the solar REB at the surface. The situation reversed in summer, when cloud TWP increased and α decreased due to sea ice melt. For values of $TWP < 70 \text{ g m}^{-2}$, and $\alpha > 0.4$, the relative impact of the cloud TWP on changes of the solar REB at the surface was generally smaller than that of the surface albedo.

1. Introduction

In the Arctic, complex interacting feedback mechanisms lead to a faster increase of the near-surface air temperature compared to the global warming. This is a major signature of a phenomenon that is referred to as Arctic amplification (Serreze et al., 2009; Previdi et al., 2021; Wendisch et al., 2023a). The combined solar and thermal-infrared radiative energy budget (REB) at the surface is one of the key factors determining the Arctic climate system and thus Arctic amplification. Here the combined REB represents the sum of net irradiances covering the solar (wavelengths between $0.3 \mu\text{m}$ and $5 \mu\text{m}$) and thermal-infrared ($3 \mu\text{m}$ and $50 \mu\text{m}$) spectral ranges. Net irradiances are determined by the difference between downward minus upward irradiances. Positive values of the REB indicate a radiative warming of the surface, negative values are related to a surface cooling by radiative processes.

Clouds and surface albedo, in combination with the solar zenith angle (SZA), are important players in regulating the solar part of the

surface REB (Curry et al., 1993; Shupe and Intrieri, 2004; Wendler et al., 2004; Perovich, 2018; Wendisch et al., 2023b). In a cloudy atmosphere and during the Arctic summer in polar day conditions, the solar REB at the surface is mostly negative due to the reflection of solar radiation by clouds. When the solar radiation is absent in the Arctic winter during polar night, the surface REB is positive in a cloudy atmosphere, mainly due to the dominance of thermal-infrared radiation, leading to a warming of the surface by emission of thermal-infrared radiation by the clouds.

The solar contribution to the REB becomes significant for a high sun (small values of SZA). Observations have revealed the important role of the surface albedo (α) and multiple scattering processes between the surface and the cloud base for the solar REB (Wendler et al., 2004). For low values of α (dark surfaces), prevailing for the sea ice-free Arctic Ocean, the surface REB is largest for cloud-free conditions, which is mainly caused by the solar portion of the REB. For highly

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reflective, bright surfaces, which are common for the sea ice-covered Arctic Ocean, the REB decreases with decreasing cloud cover, leading to radiative cooling in the absence of clouds, averaged over the day (Wendler et al., 2004; Perovich, 2018). Based on observational data, Shupe and Intrieri (2004) analyzed the effect of clouds on the surface REB using the concept of cloud radiative forcing. They found that solar cloud forcing is more sensitive to the microphysical properties of Arctic clouds in summer when SZA and α are small.

With the retreat of Arctic summer sea ice (Comiso et al., 2017; Serreze and Meier, 2019), the seasonal cycle of the surface REB changes as well, since the REB is sensitive to the radiative interactions between clouds and surface albedo. Long-term, surface-based radiation measurements allow to derive inter-annual and multi-annual changes of the surface REB. However, such long-term observations are sparse across the Arctic (Driemel et al., 2018; Ebell et al., 2020; Meloni et al., 2024). Shorter time series of ground-based radiation measurements have been collected during one-year-lasting drift expeditions using research vessels, such as the Surface Heat Budget of the Arctic (SHEBA, Uttal et al., 2002) and the Multidisciplinary drifting Observatory for the Study of Arctic Climate (MOSAiC, Shupe et al., 2022; Cox et al., 2023). These data were collected over sea ice and are not affected by local surface characteristics common for measurement at land stations. Ship-based observations are locally limited and do not provide an Arctic-wide insight into the complex radiative links between clouds and surface properties and the REB.

To quantify the separate radiative effects of parameters contributing to the solar REB at the surface, a combination of measurements and radiative transfer calculations is applied (Cawkwell and Bamber, 2002; Di Biagio et al., 2012; Barrientos-Velasco et al., 2022). Such sensitive studies, which reveal local changes, may not be fully represent the Arctic as a whole. For example, Di Biagio et al. (2012) investigated the effect of different parameters on the solar REB in cloud-free conditions using data from the Thule Air Base in Greenland. They identified late spring as the period when solar radiation is most sensitive to variations in surface albedo. For cloud-free conditions, Barrientos-Velasco et al. (2022) have quantified the response of solar irradiances and the surface REB to perturbations of different atmospheric parameters (e.g., vertical profiles of ozone, air temperature, and water vapor) against a predefined reference case based on ship-borne observations during the Arctic summer 2017. For the solar REB at the surface, they found the highest sensitivity ($\pm 31.5 \text{ W m}^{-2}$) with respect to the surface albedo, which had been varied between 0.65 ± 0.08 , while an assumed water vapor perturbation of 15% resulted in a REB variability of less than $\pm 1 \text{ W m}^{-2}$. Cawkwell and Bamber (2002) analyzed the effect of cloud cover on the modeled solar net irradiances on the Greenland ice sheet. The changes compared to the reference case included the surface albedo (± 0.02) and the cloud cover $\pm 5\%$. Their study implied that the surface albedo has a greater influence on the REB than the cloud cover. A smaller but no less significant effect was caused by different cloud types.

Such sensitivity studies depend on the reference conditions and the parameter variations assumed for a given location and time. A previous study by Loeb et al. (2019) used multi-year satellite data to decompose the variations of surface irradiances into atmospheric (mainly by clouds) and surface (by surface albedo) contributions on a monthly to inter-annual scales. These changes are considered as anomalies from the monthly means. Their method applies a model framework that approximates the Earth–atmosphere system as a single-scattering and absorbing atmospheric layer above a reflecting surface. For the Arctic Ocean, these authors concluded that the surface contribution exceeds the atmospheric one due to anomalies of the net solar surface irradiance, following the spatial patterns of the sea ice fraction.

In our study we use results from a coupled Arctic regional climate model to investigate which of the three parameters, cloud total water path, surface albedo, or solar zenith angle has the greater influence on the change of the REB. We restrict this study on the solar component

of the REB. Our approach takes into account the spatial and temporal variability of these parameters in the Arctic and selected sub-regions. In Section 2, we present the applied climate model and two methods to derive different metrics quantifying the relative impact of the cloud characteristics and surface albedo variability on the changes of the solar REB. The spatial distribution and temporal evolution of the two metrics, as well as an analysis of their potential drivers are presented in Section 3. The final Section 4 summarized the conclusions of the paper.

2. Data and methods

2.1. Coupled arctic regional climate modeling

2.1.1. Model description

Our study analyses simulations by the atmosphere–ocean coupled, Arctic regional climate model HIRHAM–NAOSIM (Dorn et al., 2019). The model serves to quantify the importance of cloud properties, surface albedo, and solar zenith angle on the solar REB at the surface. HIRHAM–NAOSIM is applied over a circum-Arctic domain using rotated latitude–longitude grid cells with a horizontal resolution of $1/4^\circ$ ($\sim 27 \text{ km}$) in the atmospheric part of HIRHAM, and $1/12^\circ$ ($\sim 9 \text{ km}$) in the ocean–sea ice component NAOSIM. Details of the model coupling and the model components are provided by Dorn et al. (2019).

The results used in our study correspond to the simulation HNnew of pair P1 described by Foth et al. (2024). The simulations were carried out for the period 2019–2020 (temporal resolution of 3 h); they were driven by ERA5 reanalysis data (Hersbach et al., 2020) at HIRHAM's lateral boundaries, as well as at HIRHAM's lower and NAOSIM's upper boundaries, which are not covered by the domain of the other model component. For the open lateral boundaries in the North Atlantic, NAOSIM applied data from the ORAS5 reanalysis (Zuo et al., 2019). To reproduce the observed synoptic and large-scale atmospheric conditions and to allow a comparison with measurements, the prognostic variables of HIRHAM (surface air pressure, air temperature, horizontal wind components, specific air humidity, cloud liquid water content, and cloud ice content) were nudged to ERA5 with a vertically uniform timescale of 16.67 h, which corresponds to a nudging of 1% per time step. The simulations of HIRHAM–NAOSIM applied the cloud parametrization described by Klaus et al. (2016), and the parametrization of the sea ice surface albedo suggested by Jäkel et al. (2019).

2.1.2. Modeled and measured solar net irradiance at the surface

The solar REB at the surface is derived from the solar net irradiance F_{net} (in units of W m^{-2}), which is calculated from the difference of downward irradiance (F^\downarrow) and upward irradiance (F^\uparrow):

$$F_{\text{net}} = F^\downarrow - F^\uparrow \quad (1)$$

Recent modifications of the surface albedo scheme have been implemented into the HIRHAM–NAOSIM model system on the basis of revised surface albedo parametrization using observational data (Jäkel et al., 2024). As part of this evaluation, the modeled net irradiances were compared with aircraft observations collected during a spring campaign called the “Polar Airborne Measurements and Arctic Regional Climate Model Simulation Project” (PAMARCMiP) in 2018. Furthermore, data from another aircraft campaign (MOSAiC Airborne observations in the Central Arctic, MOSAiC-ACA) accompanying MOSAiC were used, which took place in autumn 2020 (Mech et al., 2022). For these data, a root mean squared error (RMSE) for F_{net} of 30 W m^{-2} was derived. Two main model parameters contributed to this RMSE: the surface albedo, significantly determining the upward irradiance, and the cloud representation, controlling the upward and downward irradiances.

The scatter plot in Fig. 1a taken from Jäkel et al. (2024) shows the relationship between modeled net irradiances ($F_{\text{net,model}}$) and measured net irradiances ($F_{\text{net,meas}}$) as a function of the difference between modeled and measured surface albedo ($\Delta\alpha$) and downward irradiance

Fig. 1. (a) Scatterplot of net solar irradiance measured close to the surface, based on measured and modeled surface albedo covering the flights performed during PAMARCMiP and MOSAiC-ACA in spring and autumn. The horizontal bars indicate the standard deviation of the averaged measured $F_{\text{net,meas}}$ within the modeled grid cell. Color code gives the surface albedo difference ($\Delta\alpha = \alpha_{\text{model}} - \alpha_{\text{meas}}$) and the symbol size the difference of the modeled and measured downward irradiance (taken from Jäkel et al., 2024). (b) Same as for (a) but using helicopter-borne measurements from MOSAiC in summer.

(ΔF^{\downarrow}) for measurements collected in the Arctic during spring and autumn in 2020, when the MOSAiC expedition took place (Shupe et al., 2022). Fig. 1b provides a similar plot based on helicopter-borne measurements of F^{\downarrow} and F^{\uparrow} taken on 23 flight days in summer between May and July 2020 during MOSAiC (Pätzold et al., 2023; Sperzel et al., 2023a; Sperzel et al., 2023b). Obviously, the spread of $\Delta\alpha$ is larger for the spring and autumn with a RMSE of 0.12, compared to the results obtained for the MOSAiC data in summer (0.06). The modeled downward irradiance in spring and autumn shows a negative bias with a RMSE of 39 W m^{-2} . This bias results from an overestimation of cloud cover, while for the summer the comparison shows negative and positive differences of ΔF^{\downarrow} with RMSE = 80 W m^{-2} . Comparing the different RMSE values it is concluded that the contribution of the surface albedo is more relevant for the spring and autumn campaigns, while the correct modeling of F^{\downarrow} , and consequently the representation of clouds in the model, is more crucial for the calculation of F_{net} in Arctic summer.

2.2. Relative impacts of variability in clouds, surface albedo, and SZA

To quantify the relative impact of cloud parameters, surface albedo, and SZA on F_{net} changes, two methods are applied, which are introduced in this subsection.

2.2.1. Standardized regression coefficients in a linear regression model (LRM)

In Jäkel et al. (2024), the standardized regression coefficients of cloud parameters, surface albedo, and SZA were calculated for the two periods during the PAMARCMiP (spring 2018) and MOSAiC-ACA (autumn 2020) campaigns. As HIRHAM-NAOSIM provides the ice water path (IWP) and liquid water path (LWP), the cloud total water path (TWP = IWP + LWP), was used to characterize the modeled clouds. A linear regression model (LRM) was applied to relate F_{net} to the three variables (cloud TWP, α , and SZA). It was assumed that F_{net} is mainly a function of these three parameters. To account for the different units of these variables, the non-standardized regression coefficients b_j with j indicating either the cloud TWP, surface albedo (α), or SZA were normalized to obtain the standardized regression coefficients β_j by:

$$\beta_j = b_j \cdot \frac{\sigma_j}{\sigma_{F_{\text{net}}}}, \quad (2)$$

with σ_j and $\sigma_{F_{\text{net}}}$ representing the standard deviations of the variables and F_{net} , respectively.

The σ values were calculated from all data points used in the LRM. This implies that a change of one standard deviation in one of the variables is associated with a change of β standard deviations in

F_{net} . Thus, the dominant variable will have the maximum absolute value of β_j . Ranking the influence of the three variables on changes in F_{net} , Jäkel et al. (2024) has revealed that the strongest influence is due to surface albedo ($\beta_{\alpha} = -0.80$), followed by cloud TWP ($\beta_{\text{TWP}} = -0.38$), and SZA ($\beta_{\text{SZA}} = -0.23$). However, this ranking represents only a snapshot. We would rather expect a seasonal dependence of the standardized regression coefficients. Therefore, this study aims to analyze the seasonal cycle of the ranking of α , cloud TWP, and SZA for the whole Arctic and for the entire period between April and September 2020.

A disadvantage of this approach is that it assumes a linear relationship between independent variables. However, especially for sea ice surfaces, there are physically based correlations between cloud properties and surface albedo (Warren, 1982; Gardner and Sharp, 2010). A change in the spectral weighting of the incident radiation, caused by absorption and scattering, leads directly to a change in the surface albedo. There is an additional dependence of α on the SZA due to changes in the diffuse and direct components of the incident radiation (Gardner and Sharp, 2010). Therefore, the variables used to calculate the regression coefficients β cannot be considered completely independent.

The assumption of a linear relationship between cloud TWP, α , and SZA, with respect to F_{net} is only a rough approximation. To investigate the relationships between these three variables and F_{net} , the data were divided into classes. The F_{net} values of all cases falling into respective combinations of these classes were averaged to calculate the coefficients of determination (R^2) of the LRM. The dependence of F_{net} on SZA was analyzed for SZA classes with a step size of 2° . We found R^2 values above 0.98 for different combinations of cloud TWP and α . The two cloud TWP ranges represent thin (TWP = $30 - 40 \text{ g m}^{-2}$) and thick clouds (TWP = $80 - 100 \text{ g m}^{-2}$). The three selected ranges of α correspond to open ocean water, a mixture of melt ponds and bare ice, and snow-covered sea ice. Slightly smaller R^2 values between 0.93 and 0.98 were calculated for the linear fit between α and F_{net} for the two ranges of cloud TWP and three equidistant ranges of SZA covering 60° to 75° in steps of 5° . The cloud TWP dependence of F_{net} reveals the smallest R^2 with values between 0.83 and 0.93. In particular, a stronger decrease in F_{net} is obtained for optically thin clouds as compared to the results calculated for optically thicker clouds. However, the linear regression can be improved by using cloud TWP^{0.25} instead of cloud TWP to account for the non-linear decrease in F_{net} with increasing cloud TWP. This approach increases the R^2 for the linear fit to values between 0.95 and 1.00. In the following, the cloud TWP is taken into account in the calculation of the β parameters by using the power values of the cloud TWP with TWP^{0.25}. The results of the analyzed linear correlations are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1
Coefficients of determination (R^2) of the linear fits between F_{net} and one of the variables SZA, α or cloud TWP for selected value ranges of the two remaining variables.

		R^2 - SZA dependence			R^2 - α dependence		
		(0.0,0.15)	(0.35,0.45)	(0.75,0.85)	(60,65)	(65,70)	(70,75)
TWP (g m^{-2})	α						
	(30,40)	1.00	0.99	0.99	0.98	0.97	0.97
	(80,100)	0.99	0.99	0.98	0.95	0.94	0.93
		R^2 - TWP dependence			R^2 - TWP ^{0.25} dependence		
α	SZA ($^\circ$)						
	(60,65)				(60,65)	(65,70)	(70,75)
	(0.35,45)	0.93	0.90	0.83	1.00	0.99	0.97
	(0.75,0.85)	0.90	0.88	0.83	0.95	0.95	0.95

2.2.2. Boosted regression tree (BRT) method

As a second approach, we applied the boosted regression tree (BRT) technique, which captures cross-correlations and accounts for non-linearity. A detailed introduction to this technique is given by Elith et al. (2008). The BRT method involves a machine learning algorithm that belongs to the family of ensemble learning methods. The BRT algorithm creates multiple tree sub-models and combines them to produce an improved final model. The method uses stochastic gradient boosting whereby the model-building process is a step-wise procedure. The BRT approach fits the models hierarchically so that each member tree reduces the prediction error of the previous one. Therefore, this ensemble method improves the predictive accuracy compared to, e.g., random forest models. This enhanced performance is achieved because the next predictor is trained to improve the already trained ensemble (Elith et al., 2008).

An advantage of using ensembles of decision tree methods such as the BRT technique is that they can automatically provide estimates of the importance of features from a trained prediction model. In general, importance provides a quantitative score that indicates how useful each feature was in constructing the boosted decision trees within the model. The more frequent a feature is used for important decisions in decision trees, the greater its relative importance. In this study, the open source BRT package implemented in the Scikit-learn toolbox (Pedregosa et al., 2011) for Python was employed to derive the relative importance (I) of the cloud TWP, α , and SZA. For all realizations, the dataset was split such that that 90% of the data were used for training of the BRT model, and 10% for testing.

The performance of the BRT model was evaluated using the normalized root mean square error (NRMSE) and the R^2 by comparing the test data set of simulated F_{net} by HIRHAM-NAOSIM with the results of the BRT model. For BRT model tuning, which included several cycles of cross-validation, were performed with different settings of the number of sequential trees (n_estimators: 70 to 400), the learning rate (0.01 to 0.1), the number of nodes in the decision trees (max_depth: 4 to 5), and the minimum number of samples required to split an internal node (min_samples_split: 4 to 7). The range of settings is based on variations of the default settings that are used in the Python BRT tool. The choice of the learning rate is a compromise between accuracy and computation time. The lower the learning rate, the slower the model will learn. The advantage of a slower learning rate is that the model becomes more robust and efficient. If the learning rate is low, more trees are needed to train the model. We found similar values of R^2 (0.84) and NRMSE (0.27) using a learning rate of 0.1 and n_estimators = 70 and using the slower learning rate of 0.01 and n_estimators = 400. However, the computation time is reduced by a factor of 4.5 using the lower number of estimators and the higher learning rate. Furthermore, we found that the choice of min_samples_split and max_depth has no significant impact on the BRT model performance.

Both metrics, β and I , describe the relative impact of each variable in the proposed regression model. Changes to any of the variables that determine F_{net} will contribute to changes in F_{net} . Therefore, the relative impact of each variable on F_{net} depends on two factors: the sensitivity of F_{net} to that variable, and the variability of that variable.

3. Results of application of the two methods

The standardized regression coefficients β and the relative importance I have been calculated for three settings. Firstly, the spatial distribution of the β and I parameters based on three-hourly data from May to September per model grid cell was examined. Therefore, σ in Eq. (2) corresponds to the temporal variation per model grid cell for the period considered. Secondly, we determined β and I along the track of the research vessel *Polarstern* during MOSAiC. The model data were filtered with respect to the time and the location of the ship. For each grid cell representing the ship position and the corresponding time, we considered all modeled data points within a time window of ± 14 days. This gives a time series of β and I that can be fitted into the previous spatial distribution map. And thirdly, four different Arctic sub-regions were selected. All data points within these sub-regions and within a time period of ± 14 days were used to calculate time series of β and I to identify their temporal evolution as a function of the variables cloud TWP, α , and SZA, and their variability. Fig. 2 summarizes the outline of the three settings.

3.1. Spatial distribution

Both approaches (LRM, BRT) were applied to the cloud TWP, α , and F_{net} simulated by HIRHAM-NAOSIM for the period between April and September 2020. We have excluded data with SZA larger than 85° , i.e., cases of little or no incident solar radiation. Fig. 3 shows the spatial distribution of the standardized regression coefficient β (LRM approach), and the relative importance I (BRT model) of the three variables. A large absolute value of β means a high sensitivity of F_{net} to the respective variable. For all three β parameters (surface albedo α , cloud TWP, SZA), the values are mostly negative. This indicates that higher values of F_{net} occur for lower surface albedo, lower cloud TWP, and lower SZA, which is related to a higher downward irradiance and a lower upward irradiance. Regarding the spatial distribution of β , the strongest variability is found for β_α (surface albedo) with relatively low values in the European Arctic compared to the other regions of the Arctic Ocean.

Low β_α values are also observed over Greenland, which are common for regions that are permanently covered by snow, or for areas that are mostly ice-free (southern part of the European Arctic). In both cases, a low variability leads to low values of β_α (see Appendix A, Fig. A.9). In contrast to the spatial distribution of β_α , β_{TWP} and β_{SZA} reveal a rather uniform distribution over the whole Arctic Ocean. Lower β_{TWP} values were calculated for regions with low cloud TWP, which are also characterized by low cloud TWP variability. This is particularly evident over Greenland. The southern European Arctic reveals the highest values of β_{TWP} , where the largest mean TWPs with the highest variability occurs.

The high absolute values of β_{SZA} indicate that the largest sensitivity of F_{net} is attributed to the SZA in the period between April and September. A similar behavior was found for the distribution of the

Fig. 2. Scheme of the analysis. Model data taken from HIRHAM-NAOSIM and the SZA (calculated from time and position) are used for three different settings (spatial distribution, temporal evolution along ship track, temporal evolution for four Arctic sub-regions).

Fig. 3. (a)–(c) Maps of standardized regression coefficients (β), and (d)–(f) relative importance parameter (I) of surface albedo (a, d), cloud TWP (b, e), and SZA (c, f) with respect to the net surface irradiance from HIRHAM-NAOSIM simulations for April–September 2020. The β and I parameters calculated along the MOSAiC ship track are outlined in black. Note that the ship track regions represent ‘snapshots’ in time, different from the May to September averages shown in the background. The red-dashed box indicates the track from April to June. In (f) four regions are marked, namely the Beaufort Sea (BS), the Central Arctic (CA), the Greenland Sea (GS), and the Barents-Norwegian Sea (BNS).

relative importance (Fig. 3d–f). Very low values of I were calculated for the surface albedo in the European Arctic, where the cloud TWP shows its highest importance.

In Fig. 3, the parameters β and I along the ship track (outlined in black) are also included. Unlike before, the relative impact was calculated taking into account the time the ship has been at a particular location. Thus, the impact can be interpreted as a snapshot. The β and I for the April to September average values are assumed to have similar values to the surrounding regions. In April, *Polarstern* was at 85.5° N, 14.4° E, drifting southwards and went to Spitsbergen in early June. Subsequently, the ship returned to the original floe (82.0° N, 8.1° E), and continued to drift south between mid-June and late July, until the floe disintegrated in the Fram Strait. Finally, *Polarstern* returned to the sea ice near the North Pole to start drifting again in late August. The magnitude of the β_α and I_α along the route shows two different regimes. A higher relative impact of α is observed when the ship drifted southwards until early June (red dashed box in Fig. 3a, d),

especially during the period when the sea ice was changing rapidly due to the onset of melting. Thereafter, as *Polarstern* was relocated, the relative impact of the surface albedo on F_{net} decreased rapidly, while in turn the contribution of cloud TWP increased significantly. There is a clear discrepancy between the spatial distribution of relative impacts calculated for the whole April–September period and the results for the time window of ± 14 days along the ship track.

3.2. Temporal evolution

The relative impact of the parameters β and I additionally depend on time, which will be analyzed in this subsection. For this purpose, four different regions were selected: the Barents-Norwegian Sea (BNS), the Greenland Sea (GS), the Central Arctic (CA), and the Beaufort Sea (BS), as indicated in Fig. 3f.

To estimate the temporal evolution of β and I for the four Arctic sub-regions, all grid points within the selected area were considered

within a time window of ± 14 days. As an example, Figs. 4a and 4b show the time series of β and I for the three variables α , SZA, and cloud TWP in the central Arctic between mid-April and mid-September 2020. The relative evolution of the relative impact determined by either β or I is similar. There are four main time periods, separated by vertical dashed lines in Fig. 4. In the first period (until beginning of May), the SZA dominates F_{net} , followed by a period until end of June when the surface albedo has the largest values of I and largest absolute values of β . From the end of June on, cloud TWP becomes the main variable affecting F_{net} . Beginning in August, both cloud TWP and SZA show high relative impacts on F_{net} . The start and end of these four periods are not identical for β and I and differ by a few days. However, they are driven by the same relationship between the change in α , SZA, and cloud TWP over the whole period considered here.

Figs. 4c to 4e depict the time series of the spatial mean of surface albedo (α), solar zenith angle (SZA), and cloud total water path (TWP), and their spatial standard deviation for the central Arctic. In addition, Fig. 4f illustrates the evolution and spatial variability (standard deviation) of sea ice concentration (SIC). The dominant impact of the SZA on F_{net} until May is mainly due to the fact that the SZA is relatively large, similar to the period from August onward, when the SZA also exceeds 75° . However, the cloud TWP and its variability appear larger in August and September than in May. The second period (May–June) is characterized by the onset of melting processes, the transition from dry snow to wet snow, and the formation of melt ponds. This leads to a lower but more variable surface albedo α . The SIC is still close to 100%. The relevance of surface albedo decreases with the decrease in SIC in late June. Although temperature inversions and weak air-sea horizontal temperature gradients limit the coupling between the atmosphere and the ocean, the cloud TWP begins to increase at the same time. This is likely due to the advection of warm and moist air from lower latitudes, resulting in more moisture available for cloud formation (Kay and Gettelman, 2009). The increase in cloud TWP is associated with an increase in the LWP fraction and an increase in the LWP itself. Clouds dominated by liquid water particles tend to have a greater optical cloud depth than ice-dominated clouds, because they consist of many small droplets rather than relatively few large ice crystals. This leads to a larger cloud radiative effect, as shown by Shupe and Intrieri (2004). Unfortunately, the model does not provide information on the size of the cloud particles, which would allow a more detailed analysis of the relationship between optical cloud depth, cloud phase, and F_{net} .

The end of June indicates a turning point, as clouds begin to dominate the change in F_{net} . The values of SZA are close to minimum at that time. The same is true for α , and thus the contribution of α to the change in F_{net} is negligible for this period, since the contribution of upward irradiance to F_{net} is reduced for a low surface albedo. Therefore, the variability of downward irradiance due to cloud effects dominates. In summary, in the central Arctic during spring and early summer, the variability of the surface albedo is more important than the variability of clouds with respect to changes in F_{net} . This is mainly caused by the high surface albedo and the low cloud optical thickness and variability during that time period. This relationship is reversed in mid-summer when the surface albedo decreases due to the progressing melting and when the cloud TWP of the clouds increases.

In the following, we discuss how the results obtained for the central Arctic can be compared to the other selected regions (GS, BNS, and BS). While the mean SIC between April and September 2020 in the GS and BNS is 0.32 and 0.17, respectively, mean values of SIC of 0.72 appear in the BS, close to the value in the central Arctic (Table 2). As a result, the mean values of surface albedo are similar in the central Arctic and the Beaufort Sea. In the two European Arctic regions GS and BNS, where sea ice disappears over a large area in summer, the surface albedo was smaller than in the central Arctic and Beaufort Sea. For mean cloud TWP, we found larger values in the European Arctic than in the central Arctic and Beaufort Sea (Table 2).

Fig. 4. Time series of (a) standardized linear regression coefficient β and (b) relative importance I of surface albedo α , SZA, and cloud TWP for the area of Central Arctic. Additionally the time series of (c) surface albedo (α), (d) solar zenith angle (SZA), (e) cloud total water path (TWP), and (f) sea ice concentration (SIC) are plotted. The gray shaded areas represent the spatio-temporal standard deviations of the shown quantities. The separation between the four major periods is marked by dashed lines.

Table 2

Mean values and standard deviation of SIC, surface albedo (α), and cloud TWP for four Arctic sub-regions for the period April to September 2020.

Region	SIC	α	Cloud TWP (g m^{-2})
Central Arctic (CA)	0.73 ± 0.33	0.56 ± 0.25	76 ± 100
Beaufort Sea (BS)	0.72 ± 0.32	0.51 ± 0.25	74 ± 108
Greenland Sea (GS)	0.32 ± 0.37	0.33 ± 0.26	118 ± 148
Barents-Norwegian Sea (BNS)	0.17 ± 0.33	0.23 ± 0.24	130 ± 143

These two contrasting groups of areas (small values of α for GS/BNS versus large α for BS/CA) show similar trends in the relative impact of cloud TWP, SZA, and α to F_{net} between April and September 2020. Fig. 5 depicts a qualitatively similar evolution of β and I . In contrast to the central Arctic, changes in SZA dominate the changes in F_{net} during most of the period considered. From July onward, when α approaches its minimum and cloud TWP its maximum, the relative impact of cloud TWP changes is comparable to that of the SZA, but does not considerably exceed either the β or the I parameter of the SZA in the central Arctic. Until early May, β_α and β_{SZA} are of the same order of β_{SZA} magnitude. This does not appear for the I parameter for the two regions in the European Arctic (Fig. 5a, b). A more consistent picture of β and I parameter emerges for the Beaufort Sea (Fig. 5c). Here, the temporal evolution of β and I is similar, with a dominant SZA, interrupted only by a short period from mid to late May, when the relative impact of α reaches a maximum. Shortly after this period, the absolute value of β_{TWP} and I_{TWP} decreases rapidly, similarly as in the central Arctic. In contrast to the central Arctic, despite the increased cloud TWP and its variability, the relative importance of cloud TWP in May and early June does not dominate F_{net} changes. Instead, it is

Fig. 5. Time series of standardized regression coefficients β (upper panels) and relative importance I (lower panels) of surface albedo α , SZA, and cloud TWP for the Greenland Sea, the Barents-Norwegian Sea, and the Beaufort Sea.

Fig. 6. Correlation between the absolute value of the standardized regression coefficients $|\beta_{TWP}|$, $|\beta_{\alpha}|$, $|\beta_{SZA}|$ and the means and standard deviations (σ) of the three quantities surface albedo α , cloud TWP, and SZA. A high frequency of pairs of values is denoted by dark blue dots. The coefficient of determination R^2 of the linear regression (red line) is also given.

the SZA. Furthermore, the surface albedo plays a minor role due to its relatively low values in the two European regions GS and BNS.

3.3. Conditions that determine the relative impact

This section examines the conditions under which one of the variables (cloud TWP, α , SZA) has an increased relative impact. The time series in Fig. 4 indicated correlations between the variables cloud TWP, α , and SZA and their relative impacts on changes in F_{net} . For a quantification of these correlations, the correlation matrix between the variables and the two contribution parameters β and I was calculated based on the data derived from the time series of each region. The individual correlations are plotted in Figs. 6 and 7. Besides the mean values of cloud TWP, α , and SZA within the time window of ± 14 days of all grid points in the respective region, the standard deviation σ was included in the correlation analysis as an indicator of variability.

Most of the β parameters are negative. For better comparison with the positive I parameters, we consider their absolute values. Based on the coefficients of determination R^2 , it is found that the influence of SZA on the relative impact of cloud TWP and α to F_{net} is generally small. For β_{TWP} and I_{TWP} we see consistently high correlations with mean cloud TWP (\overline{TWP}), its standard deviation (σ_{TWP}), and mean albedo ($\bar{\alpha}$). The relative impact of cloud TWP increases when \overline{TWP} and σ_{TWP}

are large and the surface albedo is small, as is the case in July and August. An inverse relationship is found for the relative impact of surface albedo, which is highest for low \overline{TWP} and σ_{TWP} and high $\bar{\alpha}$. Unlike I_{α} , β_{α} also shows a higher R^2 for σ_{α} ($R^2 = 0.23$), meaning that a higher variability of α favors a higher relative importance of surface albedo. Such conditions appear most frequently in late spring and early summer, when snow begins to melt. This leads to variations in surface albedo due to snow of varying wetness. Later, as melt ponds begin to form, the variability in surface albedo increases further. At this point, α can drop from 0.7 to 0.4 within a few days, as shown by observations during MOSAiC (Jäkel et al., 2024; Tao et al., 2024). However, a higher surface albedo is more important than its variability for the promotion of β_{α} and I_{α} .

Smaller coefficients of determination were calculated for β_{SZA} and I_{SZA} than those derived for the β and the I parameter of TWP and α . A larger surface albedo variability, as observed in the central Arctic in late spring and early autumn when the polar day begins and ends, favors a larger relative impact of the SZA on F_{net} variations. For the other selected regions (BNS, GS, BS) a daily variation of the SZA is present throughout the period April to September. Therefore, the SZA is the dominant quantity in these regions, affecting the variability of F_{net} .

To estimate under which conditions either cloud TWP or α is more relevant to changes in F_{net} , we calculated the differences in the absolute

Fig. 7. Same as Fig. 6 but for the importance parameters I_{TWP} , I_α and I_{SZA} .

Fig. 8. Histograms of the differences in the relative impacts of surface albedo and cloud TWP for (a) the β and (b) the I parameters. Distributions are further divided into two ranges of mean cloud TWP and mean surface albedo.

values of the β and I parameters of α and cloud TWP:

$$\Delta\beta = |\beta_\alpha| - |\beta_{TWP}| \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta I = |I_\alpha| - |I_{TWP}|$$

A positive difference indicates a larger relative impact of α and a negative difference corresponds to a larger relevance of the cloud TWP. Fig. 8 shows the histograms of these differences for all data covering the four selected regions (blue step curve). The distribution shows a higher fraction of negative differences (about 70%) representing the cases dominated by the cloud TWP. Since the three variables TWP, σ_{TWP} , and $\bar{\alpha}$ show a strong correlation with the parameters β and I , we have derived thresholds for these variables to separate the data into two classes, where either the relative impact of α or the relative impact of cloud TWP exceeds the other. These thresholds were determined from the frequency distribution of each of the three variables for the two cases where $\Delta\beta$ and ΔI are either positive or negative.

Plots of these distributions are shown in Appendix B. To reduce the misclassification rate of the more relevant variable for determining F_{net} (cloud TWP or α), we used the 95% quantiles to define the lower and upper limits of the range of values of the distributions as thresholds, rather than looking at the entire distribution. These quantiles of a positive $\Delta\beta$ are 0.40 for $\bar{\alpha}$ and 93 g m^{-2} for \overline{TWP} , while for a negative $\Delta\beta$ thresholds of 0.41 ($\bar{\alpha}$) and 74 g m^{-2} (\overline{TWP}) were derived. To exclude a large part of the range in which both cases can occur, we have combined the thresholds to 70 g m^{-2} for \overline{TWP} and 0.4 for $\bar{\alpha}$.

The comparison of the misclassified cases showed that σ_{TWP} does not contribute to the improvement of the classification. Therefore, the separation has been simplified by using only thresholds for TWP and $\bar{\alpha}$. The resulting distributions of the separated differences are presented in Fig. 8 (orange and green lines). When the cloud TWP is less than about 70 g m^{-2} and α is greater than 0.4, the relative impact of α on F_{net} is, in most cases, greater than that of the cloud TWP. This is consistent for

the β and the I parameter. About 13% of the cases where ΔI and $\Delta\beta$ are greater than zero are misclassified. Improved results were obtained for positive ΔI and $\Delta\beta$ with a misclassification rate of less than 3%. Double classification is found mainly for $\Delta\beta$ and ΔI in the range between -0.2 and 0.05 . However, most cases where either surface albedo or cloud TWP has a significantly greater weight than the other variable in influencing F_{net} are well represented by the thresholds found for \overline{TWP} and $\bar{\alpha}$.

Field measurements during the two drift expeditions SHEBA and MOSAiC have shown, that a cloud TWP of less than 70 g m^{-2} is mostly present during the winter and spring seasons. In particular, Shupe et al. (2006) reported a cloud LWP greater than 70 g m^{-2} between June and September for mixed phase clouds in the Beaufort Sea during SHEBA, while the cloud IWP exceeded 50 g m^{-2} between July and September. Also during the MOSAiC expedition, the cloud LWP showed a distinct seasonal variability with seasonally averaged daily mean LWP of 25 g m^{-2} in spring (March–May) and 91 g m^{-2} in summer (June–August). Together with the decrease in surface albedo (due to the increase in ponded ice and open water areas), this emphasizes that the conditions that determine the relative impact on F_{net} are more favorable for cloud TWP relative to α in mid-Arctic summer than in spring or early summer. This finding agrees with results of Shupe and Intrieri (2004), although their study analyzed the sensitivity of solar cloud forcing instead of F_{net} . They found that solar cloud forcing is more sensitive to cloud microphysical properties in the Arctic summer when SZA and surface albedo are low.

4. Summary and conclusions

Simulations using an atmosphere-ocean coupled Arctic regional climate model were performed to analyze the dependence of changes in net surface solar irradiance (F_{net}), quantifying the solar REB at the

surface, on typical variations of the cloud total water path (TWP), surface albedo (α), and solar zenith angle (SZA). Two regression methods were used to derive parameters quantifying the relative impact of these variables on changes in F_{net} . Firstly, a linear regression model (LRM) was applied to determine standardized regression coefficients (β). Secondly, a machine learning method (boosted regression tree, BRT) was used to derive the impact (I) of the three variables. β and I represent metrics of the relative impact of the individual variables cloud TWP, α , and SZA on F_{net} . While the LRM has the disadvantage of assuming a linear relationship between independent variables, which is not necessarily fulfilled, the BRT technique captures non-linear linkages between the variables that drive F_{net} . It is concluded that the LRM and the BRT method provide comparable results in estimating the spatio-temporal evolution of the relative impact of α and cloud TWP on F_{net} changes. This supports the assumption that nonlinear effects between the analyzed variables are of minor importance with respect to their relative impact on F_{net} . This conclusion does not concur with the general nonlinear dependence of cloud radiative effects.

The spatial distribution of β and I for the period from April to September 2020 showed the largest variability for the relative impact of α , with large values in the central Arctic and the Beaufort Sea, and small values in the Greenland and Barents-Norwegian Sea. Overall, the SZA was found to be the most important variable influencing F_{net} , also showing the lowest spatial variability over the Arctic Ocean relative to cloud TWP and α . The temporal evolution of β and I is driven by the seasonal cycle of cloud TWP, α , and SZA.

The following main conclusions are drawn from our study:

- The relative impact of the surface albedo α on the solar radiative energy budget (expressed in the form of the net surface solar irradiance F_{net}) is largest in spring after the onset of melting, when the cloud total water path (TWP) is still small. Surface albedo becomes dominant when the solar zenith angle (SZA) variability is small and sea ice concentration is large.
- The variability of cloud TWP dominates the variability of F_{net} in summer when cloud TWP increases due to larger availability of air moisture, and when the surface albedo is strongly reduced by sea ice melt and decreasing sea ice concentration.
- The SZA is the dominant factor in F_{net} variations where the SZA variability is large, such as outside the central Arctic.

We have identified thresholds of cloud TWP and α at which the relative impact of cloud TWP or α on F_{net} exceeds the other. Specifically, for a cloud TWP less than about 70 g m^{-2} and a surface albedo greater than $\alpha = 0.4$, the relative impact of α on F_{net} is generally greater than that of the cloud TWP. The reverse is true when the cloud TWP is greater than the threshold of 70 g m^{-2} and the surface albedo is less than 0.4.

With regard to an increasingly warmer Arctic in the future, we expect an increase in optically thicker clouds and a decrease in surface albedo for larger areas of the Arctic and for a longer period of time in the year. It, therefore, can be projected that the threshold values for a cloud-dominated F_{net} will increasingly be reached. As a consequence, it can be assumed that the role of clouds in the surface solar radiative energy budget and for Arctic amplification will become more significant over the course of the sunlight season.

Similar studies using different models would need to investigate to which extent our results depend on the chosen model. As with any model-based dataset, including reanalysis data, there are model biases. Several studies have evaluated the HIRHAM-NAOSIM model using MOSAiC measurement data (Aue et al., 2023; Foth et al., 2024; Jäkel et al., 2024), demonstrating that the model can reproduce processes in a manner that allows us to assess the effect of surface albedo and TWP on changes to F_{net} . Furthermore, it would be advantageous to apply the two regression methods to MOSAiC measurement data. But this requires collocated irradiance and cloud microphysics data, which are not available consistently for the entire Arctic summer season.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Evelyn Jäkel: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Tim R. Sperzel:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Formal analysis. **Manfred Wendisch:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Kevin Wolf:** Writing – review & editing, Software. **Astrid Lampert:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Gerit Birnbaum:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Wolfgang Dorn:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Evelyn Jäkel reports financial support was provided by German Research Foundation. Tim R. Sperzel reports financial support was provided by Federal Ministry of Education and Research Bonn Office. Wolfgang Dorn reports financial support was provided by European Union. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Spatial distribution of means and variabilities

In addition to the calculated β and I parameter, the mean values and the standard deviation of surface albedo, cloud TWP, and SZA for each model grid cell are shown (see Fig. A.9).

Appendix B. Frequency distributions of means and TWP variability

The frequency distributions of mean TWP, mean α and σ_{TWP} when either cloud TWP or α has a greater impact on F_{net} variability are shown below. The respective 95% quantiles (vertical dashed lines) indicate the thresholds between the two states (see Fig. B.10).

Data availability

The modeling data of HIRHAM-NAOSIM data are available from Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10781301>; Dorn and Jäkel (2024).

Fig. A.9. Maps of mean values and standard deviations of surface albedo (a, d), cloud TWP (b, e) and SZA (c, f) from HIRHAM-NAOSIM simulations for April-September 2020.

Fig. B.10. Histograms of (a) mean cloud TWP, (b) mean α , (c) σ_{TWP} . The distribution of all cases with a higher relative impact of TWP compared to β_α are shown in green, the data with a higher relative impact of α compared to β_{TWP} in orange. Dashed lines indicate the 95% quantiles used to determine the thresholds.

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